

Kinetic Measurements of Charge Transfer Reactions of Benzocaine, Procaine and Lignocaine with Chloranil and Bromanil in different Solvents

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Kinetic studies have been done by spectrophotometric and conductivity methods for chloranil and bromanil complexes of benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine in different solvents. From the variation of specific rate constants with dielectric constants of the medium the excited state dipole moments for the complexes have been calculated.

LITERATURE reports are scanty regarding the complex forming properties of local anaesthetics.

Eckert reported that procaine hydrochloride formed a complex with caffeine¹, and spectroscopic measurements showed that charge transfer occurred when procaine hydrochloride was the donor and caffeine the acceptor. Nmr studies of molecular complexes of some local anaesthetics with 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene and 2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-1,4-dicyanobenzene have been reported². Some investigations were carried out in this direction where a charge-transfer type of interaction was indicated³.

In our earlier work⁴, we had studied a series of local anaesthetic compounds (benzocaine, lignocaine and procaine) having closely related structures, and tested whether there was any relation between charge-transfer complexes formed with a given second compound (chloranil, bromanil, iodanyl or 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene). We had observed that the optical densities at the λ_{max} assigned for different systems changed with time, depending on the dielectric constant of the solvents. For the benzocaine system, the time dependency of optical density was observed in a highly polar solvent like dimethylformamide (dc=36.7). For the procaine system such a dependency was observed for chloroform (dc=4.8) and for higher dielectrics. For lignocaine, the time dependency was observed for non-polar solvents such as carbon tetrachloride (dc=2.21). This interesting observation prompted us to undertake the kinetic investigations of these systems in different solvents.

In the present paper, we report the effect of solvent dielectrics on the reaction kinetics of benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine with chloranil/bromanil, both by spectrophotometric and conductometric methods. From these studies, the dipole moments of the transition state of the complexes have been estimated.

Experimental

Benzocaine (Jyoti Chemical) procaine and lignocaine (Sigma) were used as such. Chloranil (E. Merck) was used after several recrystallisations from chloroform and its purity was checked by determination of the melting point. Bromanil was prepared by the standard method⁵. The solvents carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane, dichloroethane, dimethylformamide and dimethyl sulphoxide were thoroughly dried and distilled⁶.

Spectral measurements were done on Cary 17D and Cary 2390 spectrophotometers. Conductances were measured on a Phillips conductivity bridge with a specially designed cell having bright platinum electrodes. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

The reaction was found to be unimolecular as shown by linear plots of $\log [(M_\infty - M_0)/(M_\infty - M_t)]$ vs t , where M is absorbance or conductance respectively and t the time. From the slope of the curve, the specific rate constants (k_1) were calculated.

Measurements of dipole moments of transition state were done utilising Laidler and Eyring model of the form,

$$\log k_1 = \log \left(K \frac{kT}{h} K_0^* \right) - \frac{1}{kT} \left(\frac{D-1}{2D+1} \right) \left[\frac{\mu_A^2}{a_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{a_B^3} - \frac{\mu_{M^*}^2}{a_{M^*}^3} \right] \quad (1)$$

where the terms have their usual significance.

Results and Discussion

The band positions of the complexes of different donors (benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine) with acceptors chloranil and bromanil, are listed in Table 1. These generally consist of a series of absorption bands ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4$). Some of the λ_1

TABLE I—POSITIONS OF DIFFERENT BANDS FOR DONORS WITH DIFFERENT ACCEPTORS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Donors	Acceptors	Solvent*	λ_1 nm	λ_2 nm	λ_3 nm	$\bar{\nu}_{CT}$ $\times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	λ_4 nm
Benzocaine	Chloranil	DMF	422	448	545	18.35	390
		DMSO	—	—	530	18.86	408
		DMF : DMSO=1 : 1	422	448	540	18.52	405
		DMF : DMSO=1 : 2	422	448	540	18.52	408
		DCE : DMF=1 : 2	422	448	540	18.52	405
	Bromanil	DMF	422	448	550	18.18	400
		DMSO	—	—	550	18.18	405
		DMF : DMSO=1 : 1	422	448	550	18.18	408
		DMF : DMSO=1 : 2	422	450	550	18.18	405
		DCE : DMF=1 : 2	422	450	540	18.52	400
Procaine	Chloranil	CCl ₄	—	—	500	20	—
		CHCl ₃	425	450	500, 660	20, 15.15	—
		DCM	425	450	510, 665	19.69, 15.04	—
		DCE	425	450	510, 665	19.61, 15.04	—
		DCM : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	425	450	500, 662	20, 15.10	—
		DCE : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	425	450	508, 662	19.68, 15.10	—
		CCl ₄	—	—	500	20	—
	Bromanil	CHCl ₃	425	450	500, 660	20, 15.15	—
		DCM	425	450	508, 662	19.68, 15.10	—
		DCE	425	450	508, 662	19.68, 15.10	—
		DCM : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	425	450	505, 661	19.80, 15.13	—
		DCE : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	425	450	505, 661	19.80, 15.13	—
		CCl ₄	—	—	500	20	—
		CHCl ₃	425	450	500, 660	20, 15.15	—
Lignocaine	Chloranil	CCl ₄	400	—	640	15.62	—
		CHCl ₃	400	—	660	15.15	—
		DCM	422	448	620	16.13	—
		DCE	422	448	625	16	—
		DCE : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	422	448	630	15.87	—
	Bromanil	CCl ₄	420	—	640	15.62	—
		CHCl ₃	430	—	645	15.50	—
		DCM	420	450	620	16.13	—
		DCE	420	450	620	16.13	—
		DCE : CHCl ₃ =1 : 1	420	450	615	16.26	—

*DMF=Dimethylformamide ; DMSO=dimethyl sulphoxide ; DCE=dichloroethane ; DCM=dichloromethane.

and λ_3 bands decay at a faster rate than the remainder of the absorption and are dependent on the particular acceptor, irrespective of donors. In some systems, the bands λ_1 and λ_2 are either absent, or else do not appear as discrete maxima. These bands are compared with the spectra of the sodium or potassium salt of the free radical ion derived by the acquisition of one electron (A^-). The close correspondence confirms Slifkin's conclusion⁸ that this part of the spectrum is due to the species A^- .

The band at λ_3 appears just after the donor and acceptor are mixed together. The intensity of this band gradually increases with time and it is assigned as the charge-transfer band. Owing to the unavailability of the ionisation potential or HFMO/ β values of the donors, we have plotted $\bar{\nu}_{CT}$ of chloranil complexes of benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine against $\bar{\nu}_{CT}$ of bromanil complexes of the same donors, and obtained a straight line with unit gradient (Fig. 1), indicating the charge transfer nature of the complexes⁴. We already established the charge-transfer nature of these complexes in our previous paper⁹.

For the benzocaine+chloranil/bromanil system, a band at λ_4 appears whose intensity rapidly increases to a very high value. Similar observations were made by Fulton and Lyons⁹ and Saucin and

Fig. 1. Plot of $\bar{\nu}_{CT}$ of chloranil complexes of (1) benzocaine (in DMF), (2a and 2b) procaine and (3) lignocaine (in CHCl₃) vs $\bar{\nu}_{CT}$ of bromanil complexes of same donors.

Vorst¹⁰. Slifkin's observation⁶ on the degradation of chloranil spectra to chloranilic acid is worth mentioning. In our earlier work, we reported the appearance of this type of multiple charge transfer bands¹¹. In the case of procaine and lignocaine, the situation is different because of some side-reactions.

In the procaine+chloranil/bromanil system, it was observed that the band at ~500 nm disappeared quickly and a new band around ~640 nm appeared simultaneously. The following reaction scheme may be proposed,

Thus the band at 500 nm is due to the formation of an outer complex, whereas the latter (~640 nm) is due to the formation of an inner complex in accordance with Mulliken's idea¹². The wave numbers corresponding to these bands are used in the ν_{CT} plots (Fig. 1), indicating the CT nature of the complex.

The absorption spectra of the procaine-chloranil complex in DCM at different times is shown in Fig. 2. Similar spectra for the other systems in different solvents have been obtained. The kinetics of the reaction were followed by monitoring the change in the intensity of the band at λ_s . The specific rate constants are given in Table 2.

In accordance with the Eyring equation, plots of $\log K_1$ against $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ (where D is the dielectric constant of the solvent) are fairly linear,

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of procaine-chloranil complex in dichloromethane at different time: (a) $t=0$ and (b) $t=20$ min.

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS FOR DONORS WITH CHLORANIL AND BROMANIL IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Donor	Solvents	$\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$	Specific rate constants (k_1)							
			$\times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$				$\log k_1$			
			Chloranil		Bromanil		Chloranil		Bromanil	
		From O.D.	From cond.	From O.D.	From cond.	From O.D.	From cond.	From O.D.	From cond.	
Benzocaine	DCE : DMF (1 : 2) ($\epsilon=27.866$)	0.4735	45.50	7.35	45.10	11.94	-2.34	-3.13	-2.34	-2.92
	DMF ($\epsilon=36.7$)	0.4798	40.30	11.09	47.70	17.84	-2.39	-2.95	-2.32	-2.74
	DMF : DMSO (1 : 1) ($\epsilon=42.8$)	0.4826	58.44	9.32	58.29	12.52	-2.23	-3.03	-2.23	-2.90
	DMF : DMSO (1 : 2) ($\epsilon=44.83$)	0.4834	68.51	10.62	71.90	15.35	-2.16	-2.97	-2.14	-2.81
Procaine	DMSO ($\epsilon=48.9$)	0.4848	85.78	29.78	241.8	41.91	-2.07	-2.53	-1.62	-2.38
	CHCl_3 ($\epsilon=4.81$)	0.3587	3.548	—	0.96	6.28	-1.45	—	-2.02	-1.20
	DCM : CHCl_3 (1 : 1) ($\epsilon=6.945$)	0.3992	3.29	4.26	1.77	3.14	-1.48	-1.37	-1.75	-1.50
	DCE : CHCl_3 (1 : 1) ($\epsilon=7.505$)	0.4063	4.03	8.12	1.40	2.81	-1.39	-1.09	-1.85	-1.55
	DCM ($\epsilon=9.08$)	0.4217	3.55	3.75	1.55	3.83	-1.45	-1.42	-1.81	-1.42
	DCE ($\epsilon=10.2$)	0.4299	4.91	10.74	2.56	4.98	-1.31	-1.97	-1.59	-1.30
Lignocaine	CCl_4 ($\epsilon=2.21$)	0.2232	28.78	—	26.32	—	-2.54	—	-2.58	—
	CHCl_3 ($\epsilon=4.81$)	0.3587	11.97	47.21	8.82	24.18	-2.92	-2.32	-3.05	-2.61
	DCE : CHCl_3 (1 : 1) ($\epsilon=7.505$)	0.4063	6.80	45.48	8.85	29.36	-3.16	-2.34	-3.05	-2.53
	DCM ($\epsilon=9.08$)	0.4217	17.58	82.90	19.34	41.26	-2.75	-2.08	-2.71	-2.38
	DCE ($\epsilon=10.2$)	0.4299	17.27	46.06	15.43	31.98	-2.76	-2.33	-2.81	-2.49

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log k_1$ vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ for chloranil complexes of benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine in different solvents: (O; Δ) lignocaine-chloranil complex, (●; \square) procaine-chloranil complex, (⊙; \blacktriangledown) benzocaine-chloranil complex; (a) from conductance, (b) from O.D.

TABLE 3—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF THE TRANSITION STATE FOR THE COMPLEXES

Donor	Dipole moment of the donor D	Dipole moment of the acceptor D	Dipole moment of the transition state (μ^*) D		Dipole moment of the no-bond structure (μ_1) D	Dipole moment of the dative structure (μ_2) D	b		b^2	
			O.D. data	Cond. data			From O.D.	From cond.	From O.D.	From cond.
Acceptor : Chloranil										
Benzocaine	1.82		13.47	13.47	2.57	15.35	0.842 6	0.842 6	0.710 0	0.710 0
Procaine	2.02	0.75	12.92	13.87	2.77	15.35	0.813 1	0.850 3	0.661 2	0.723 1
Lignocaine	2.86		10.69	10.30	3.61		0.679 1	0.660 1	0.461 2	0.435 8
Acceptor : Bromanil										
Benzocaine	1.82		12.72	13.60	1.82	15.35	0.842 6	0.876 0	0.710 0	0.767 4
Procaine	2.02	0	12.71	13.40	2.02	15.35	0.834 5	0.861 0	0.696 4	0.741 3
Lignocaine	2.86		12.40	11.72	2.86		0.788 3	0.759 7	0.621.5	0.577 1

for all the systems studied (Fig. 3). From the slopes of the linear plots, the dipole moments of the transition states were estimated for the complexes. Since the dipole moment values of benzocaine, procaine and lignocaine were not available in the literature, we have calculated them from the respective bond moments, by the vector addition method. The dipole moment of chloranil was taken from the literature (0.75). For bromanil, no literature data was available. Considering the symmetrical structure of bromanil and the very small value for chloranil, we have taken the dipole moment of bromanil as zero. The dipole moments of the transition states given in Table 3 are the values obtained from O.D. data and conductance data. For the calculations, the Onsager model for liquid dielectrics was used, and the a values for donors and acceptors were set equal to their molecular radius (calculated from the molecular volume), while that for the activated complex was set equal to the sum of radii of the constituents. It is to be pointed out that there may be some error in the dipole moment values, since we have taken the Onsager cavity as spherical. As there is no steady equilibrium, anisotropy of the cavity could not be estimated in the manner suggested

by Revail and Thiebaut¹³. The calculated dipole moment of the transition state is thus higher than the sum of the dipole moments of the constituents.

According to Mulliken's theory, the ground state of the charge-transfer complex is represented by

$$\psi_g = a \psi_0 + b \psi_1 \quad (3)$$

where the first term gives the contribution of the no-bond structure and the second term gives the contribution of the dative charge transfer structure. The dipole moment is given as

$$\int \psi_g \mu \psi_g dx = a^2 \int \psi(DA) \mu \psi(DA) dx + 2ab \int \psi(DA) \mu \psi(D^+A^-) dx + b^2 \int \psi(D^+A^-) \mu \psi(D^+A^-) dx \quad (4)$$

The first term gives the dipole moment of the constituents, the third term gives the dipole moment of the dative structure which is 15.35 D for the constituents separated by 3.2 Å. As the no-bond and dative functions do not overlap, the second term is set equal to zero. It is possible to estimate b from the dipole moment values obtained by Eyring's method. Table 3 shows that the percentage of charge transfer in the transition state is quite large.

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